

Different genes involved in plant hormone transduction in comparison groups related to fan-shaped inflorescence in pineapple. **(a)** The plant hormone transduction of FIs vs CIs. **(b)** The plant hormone transduction of F1b vs C1b. **(c)** The plant hormone transduction of F1a vs C1a. **(d)** The plant hormone transduction of F1b vs FIs. **(e)** The plant hormone transduction of F1a vs F1b. The pineapple DEGs (Light green, red, yellow, and dark green represent no, up-regulation, down-regulation, and up-/down-regulation of differential genes, respectively.) involved in the pathway was identified by BLASTx (E-value of less than 10⁻⁵).

a

b

c

d

e

